

Operationalising HPC tasks for space weather forecasting using Celery and Django: Making automated, HPC-powered scientific results accessible in near-real time.

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Forecasting space weather conditions in the Earth's ionosphere is critical to protecting key infrastructure, such as satellite-based positioning and navigation systems, high frequency radio communications, and the electric power grid. Variations in space weather are caused by coronal mass ejections from the Sun's surface, travelling up to 5 million kilometres per hour towards the Earth, energising electrons in the ionosphere to produce disturbances in communications and electrical systems, as well as spectacular aurorae.

Figure 1: 2D contour plots of (clockwise from top-left) vertically integrated electron density, vTEC; maximum usable frequency MUF3000; critical F2 layer frequency, foF2; and height of the critical F2 layer frequency, hmF2, generated in near real-time by assimilating GNSS data from over 2000 stations at a 5-minute frequency on a single node using 72 Intel IceLake CPU cores.

In conjunction with the University of Birmingham's SERENE group, we present a system for operationalizing HPC tasks for data assimilation in space weather forecasting using Celery and Django. Celery is a distributed task queue that allows us to execute tasks asynchronously, while Django is a popular Python-based web framework. Our system integrates both these tools to automate the process of downloading satellite data, running the data assimilation and then presenting outputs to a website in near real time. We run this end-to-end process on the University of Birmingham's BlueBEAR HPC cluster, utilising up to 3 nodes with 72 Intel IceLake CPU cores each. The website is also hosted on-site on a virtual machine running on OpenStack.

Celery is used to download observational data from hundreds of GNSS and GIRO stations around the world, in which the following assimilation step ingests up to 250 gigabytes of data per hour. Then, Celery sends multiple assimilation and forecast jobs to the Slurm scheduler, which is brokered by a RabbitMQ server. Celery is also used to create visualisations and automate file cleanup in the background, with their tasks separated into a different task queue.

The Django website is designed to be modular and flexible and provides an intuitive web interface for users to submit and monitor their jobs, as well as visualise results (Figure 1 and 2). It allows users to access automated assimilation outputs with 5, 90-minute and daily latencies, as well as forecasts. Users are also able to define and execute their custom simulations with a run-on-request function.

Figure 2: Flowchart summarizing the HPC tasks distributed and executed asynchronously by Celery, operationalizing an automated end-to-end process that starts from data acquisition, through to running simulations on HPC, and ends with visualization of outputs in near-real time via a Django website.

In summary, this project demonstrates that Celery and Django are powerful and flexible tools for operationalising HPC tasks for data assimilation in space weather forecasting. It enables users to efficiently utilize HPC resources while providing an easy-to-use website for interacting with jobs and simulation outputs in near-real time. Our system applies to a wide range of HPC tasks in research software and we believe could potentially be a useful framework for researchers to operationalise similar workflows.

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